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Introduction –

Waste management in broad terms refers to those practices that are responsible for the **disposing, processing, destroying, controlling, recycling or reusing of waste** produced by homes, various industries and healthcare facilities. And, in a city that produces around **6,300 metric tonnes** of waste every single day (Pinto, 2023), waste management policies and practices become highly integral and unavoidable to implement. These policies need to ensure sustainability in the form of averting potential health and environmental risks that accompany the waste produced, whether that be solid waste (waste produced by homes), industrial waste, nuclear waste, electronic waste or biomedical waste. One of the most hazardous types of waste, that is being produced in increasing quantities over the recent years is biomedical waste.

Biomedical waste (BMW) can be defined as any waste that is produced at the time of:

1. **diagnosis** – such as gloves, syringes, blood or urine taken during tests, cotton swabs, etc.
2. **treatment** – such as catheters, food pipes, medicines, waste produced through chemotherapy processes, anything disposable that is used in surgeries, etc.
3. **immunization of human beings/animals** – such as vaccine bottles, syringes, etc.

BMW also includes any waste that is produced during research activities in **medical or research laboratories** as well as the waste that is generated in the **production or testing** of biologics. BMW can be hazardous, pathological or infectious. While some types of waste could come under all 3 of these categories, others could be more specific to one of them and thus, these terms cannot be used interchangeably. The World Health Organisation (WHO) has further classified BMW into 8 categories – **general, pathological, radioactive, chemical, infectious, sharps, pharmaceuticals and pressurised**. The major sources of BMW include hospitals, nursing homes, healthcare centres, veterinary clinics, animal research centres and biotechnological institutes. Other minor sources are physicians, dental clinics, dermatology clinics, animal slaughterhouses, vaccination centres, blood camps, funeral homes, morgues and institutions for differently abled people.

In recent times, BMW has emerged as a major cause of concern and its production has seen a **50% increase since the COVID-19** Pandemic. According to the Times of India, around **18,000 to 21,000 kg** of BMW is produced per day. The improper management of bio-medical waste can lead to the **spreading of infectious diseases** like Tetanus, Hepatitis B & C and AIDS through exposure to healthcare workers and waste collectors while also posing a **threat to the**

public and the environment. Thus, the Ministry of Environment Forest & Climate Change in March 2016 came up with the **Biomedical Waste Management Rules, 2016 (BMWM Rules, 2016)** to ensure that every healthcare facility was taking all the necessary steps to handle BMW with utmost care. The BMWM Rules, 2016 provide comprehensive guidelines for healthcare facilities, vendors, and industries that are involved in the transportation, collection, utilization, sending and disposal of waste in a way that ensures safety from potential risks. Despite this, the lack of awareness and inappropriate techniques of disposal have caused a great threat.

Review of Literature –

(Priya Datta, 2018, pp. 6-14) in their article offer a critical view on the new, elaborate and stringent **rules of BMW disposal, 2016** which have focused on improving waste segregation, transportation, packaging and disposal methods. The new regulations see many positive changes in BMW management. For one, the methods involved at every step of the management process have been enhanced to **improve the quality of efforts** taken. Along with this, the **scope** of BMW management guidelines has been extended to include blood donation, vaccination and surgical camps. The stricter rules have also ensured that **no secondary handling** takes place during transport and that there is **no theft or misappropriation** of recyclable medical waste. Additionally, **regular monitoring** by the Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change and State Pollution Control Boards makes certain that there is compliance with the BMWM rules, 2016. An **advisory committee** to oversee the implementation of the rules has been mandated to meet every 6 months. Emphasis has also been placed on **proper budget allocation** by the government for the establishment and maintenance of competent BMW management systems in a way that reduces the volume and toxicity of the waste. Further, **manufacturers are to produce environmentally sustainable medical devices** that ensure the safest disposal possible while keeping in mind pollution control measures, addressing health challenges and the climate change crisis, all of which are highlighted in the WHO handbook. **NGOs** too play an important role in contributing to waste management practices that reduce environmental and health costs. However, the efficiency and commitment to the cause of everyone involved in the process are still under question. **International agreements and conventions** such as the Basel Convention on Hazardous Waste, Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) and Minamata Convention on Mercury have also impacted the BMWM practices in India.

Yet, this set of rules from 2016 is also accompanied by a set of challenges and this too has been prominently explored in the article. A major criticism is that government hospitals and small healthcare facilities are expected to bear an **immense financial burden** due to the high costs associated with the management of chlorinated plastic bags, gloves and blood bags within a short timeframe. The potential **environmental hazards caused by the incinerators** which emit toxic air pollutants and produce ash are also another criticism since they raise public safety and health concerns. Challenges are also related to the need for the development of additional **Common Biomedical Waste Treatment Facilities (CBMWTF)** which are crucial to meet the growing demand for the safe disposal and treatment of BMW in India. The article shows that the new rules are a major step forward and have addressed several previously existing limitations and yet, there is a long way to go to ensure complete sustainability.

(Singh, 2001, pp. 1297–1298) and (C. N. Ray, 2001, pp. 105–107) are two **case studies** conducted in the same year - 2001, one in **Delhi and the other in Ahmedabad**. These case studies despite not being the most recent, nor being post the BMW rules of 2016, offer valuable insight into the problems that plague BMW management to this day. In the Delhi case study, the **delay in waste disposal, improper segregation, financial and managerial constraints in installing incinerators** for disposal and the staff handling waste management being **untrained and inadequate** are all cited as serious issues for BMW. The Ahmedabad case study further finds that the **lack of government guidance** and disposal being handled by temporary staff have led to BMW being mixed with solid waste and ending up in landfills untreated. The most important step of waste management, i.e., **segregation of the waste is not being followed by 60% of hospitals** in both Delhi and Ahmedabad. In fact, in Ahmedabad, it was found that **one-fourth of the doctors interviewed were not even aware** of basic waste segregation. This is despite the Biomedical Waste (Management and Handling) Rules, 1998 specifying different coloured bags for the different types of medical waste. In Ahmedabad, almost **90% of the hospitals do not have incineration facilities** and the ones that do have generally found that the incinerators don't function properly. In Delhi, the situation isn't any better, out of the 25 hospitals surveyed, 10 had not taken up any incineration systems and many others burnt their waste in an open area or on their terraces. In fact, in Delhi, most of the hospitals dump their waste in the nearest garbage bins which **end up in a landfill** in Ghazipur, while others carry the waste in a rickshaw and dump it somewhere near the Yamuna River.

Only 40% of the doctors in the Ahmedabad research sample were aware of the diseases that can be contracted through improper waste management, as were the nurses but the sweepers and ragpickers were illiterate and had little to no awareness of the hazards. It was found that the ragpickers have contracted diseases like **worm infestations, viral hepatitis, skin diseases and gastroenteritis** while sorting out recyclable materials from waste bins filled with contaminated and toxic waste. Without the existence and monitoring of adequate BMWM guidelines, hospitals are using their methods of disposal, and this is acting counterproductive to safety, health and environmental concerns. And, as both articles point out the volume of biomedical waste is only going to increase with the increasing pace of urbanisation, making it integral to have better legislation in place.

Since then, better legislation has indeed implemented in 2016. Yet, the concerns circling BMWM have to be addressed and solved. (K. Suresh, 2023) in their article discuss the sustainable management of BMW through a **case study in Chennai** which focuses on the importance of appropriate techniques for treating different types of medical waste to achieve **cost savings, energy recovery, capital cost recovery and reduction of the volume** of waste produced. The case study finds that many healthcare facilities lack **on-site waste treatment** systems due to limited space within the clinical premises and concerns regarding high pollutant emissions. Moreover, in most cases, BMW is **stored for more than 48 hours**, which as per regulations is not allowed since it can lead to potential health and environmental risks. Another issue exists with **transportation** which is not as safe and efficient as it should be causing father hazards to health and the environment. Though the 2016 guidelines assure an advisory committee to ensure regulatory compliance, the guidelines regarding handling, treatment and disposal are not stringently followed since **no legal consequences or penalties** are faced by healthcare facilities for wrongly disposing of the waste.

The article also provides certain solutions. For one, the BMWM Rules, 2016 can be amended to include a mandate for a **suitable area of waste treatment within healthcare premises** during the construction stage itself. This will make healthcare facilities more self-sufficient to handle their own waste and reduce reliance on external agencies while also reducing hazards linked with transportation. The rules must also clearly emphasize which **treatment techniques** are to be used for the different types of waste produced. Additionally, the **3Rs – Reduce, Reuse, Recycle**, can be applied to BMWM too through the minimising of waste, sterilizing of certain medical equipment to reuse it and recycling waste into energy for environmental protection. Another suggestion made in the article is that **neighbouring clinics can use the hospital**

treatment facilities at a fair cost which can aid in cost recovery and additional income for the hospitals. Along with this, healthcare workers need to be **educated and made aware** of how to handle waste safely and efficiently. One of the most effective techniques for dealing with medical waste is through **Plasma Pyrolysis**. This involves turning any type of organic waste like solid, biological or hazardous waste into environment-friendly, commercially useful by-products through extreme heat generated by the plasma. In the process of Plasma Pyrolysis, medical waste is exposed to a plasma arc, which leads to the pyrolysis of said waste into gases like CO, H₂, and hydrocarbons. Then these gases are consumed to produce high temperatures up to 1200 °C. Subsequently, these hot gases are cooled down during the process to prevent the formation of dioxins and furans, ensuring reliable and safe waste disposal, which is also cost-effective. Other highly effective methods are autoclaving and microwaving. **Autoclaving** refers to a wet thermal disinfection method used for reusable medical equipment. This method is used only for highly contagious waste like microbiological sharps or cultures because it has the ability to only process a small volume of waste effectively. Autoclaves are reserved for sterilizing equipment by subjecting it to high-pressure steam. **Microwave** is a newer technology that is used to inactivate germs from medical waste. Compared to traditional autoclaves, this is a more cost-effective option and saves energy too.

Along with posing a significant healthcare crisis worldwide, the **COVID-19 Pandemic** also led to an unprecedented surge in the volume of BMW. (Malini R. Capoor, 2021, pp. 171-178) in their article highlights the need to effectively manage COVID-19 waste in order to mitigate public health risks and environmental hazards. During the Pandemic, **home quarantine, isolation wards, intensive caring units and testing laboratories** all became major sources of BMW, creating waste at a drastically higher rate than ever before. In fact, the sudden increase in waste not only added **a strain on the existing BMW systems** but also exposed the **weakness of these systems** and the **inadequate infrastructure** that is responsible for issues regarding the timely and safe disposal of waste. The increased use of **biocidal agents** and single-use **PPE kits** exacerbated environmental issues, while also contributing to land and water pollution. The problem with contamination was even more intense with COVID-19 since improper segregation and disposal could potentially lead to the **virus infecting healthcare workers, waste handlers, and the general public**. This was also a bigger issue since even households were creating infectious, medical waste at rates higher than before. The general public being largely unaware of practices regarding BMW management only further added to this issue. During the Pandemic in fact, as the article points out, the definition of BMW also

needs to consider **solid waste if it has been contaminated by bodily secretions or fluids of COVID-19 patients** such as tissues, gloves, masks, etc. Moreover, **adherence to existing regulations was a challenge** felt at a more heightened level too during the Pandemic since adapting to other unique challenges brought on by the virus was prioritised much more than transportation, disposal or management of the waste.

Several **national and international organizations** like The Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) of India, WHO, Centres for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) and the Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) in the United States have given guidelines and recommendations to deal with the challenges of COVID-19 waste management. Their major recommendations include **on-site treatment** whenever possible, **proper training and education programs** for those handling the waste as well as the **use of designated COVID-19 waste containers**. The safe disposal of PPE, liquid waste and dead bodies while **avoiding contamination of water bodies** and adhering to regulations regarding water treatment is also covered under these guidelines. Like most, this article too underlines the need for **stringent monitoring systems** that ensure compliance with guidelines at all levels. This includes regular audits, record keeping and supervision by authorities responsible for enforcing compliance. Another suggestion mentioned in the article is **effective collaboration and communication** through the establishment of channels for reporting and addressing BMWM concerns between stakeholders, including healthcare facilities, waste management authorities and regulatory agencies.

Methodology –

The **systematic approach or set of procedures** used to conduct research inquiry is known as the methodology. It includes the research design, the data collection, the analysis and the interpretation process. **Primary data collection** refers to data that is gathered directly from original sources through methods like surveys, interviews or observations. On the other hand, **secondary data collection** is the gathering of data from already existing sources such as journals, research papers, and books among others, for interpretation and analysis.

For this research, the methodology employed involved a **mixed methods approach** wherein majorly primary data collection was used along with secondary data collection for contextual understanding. The primary data collection was carried out through **personal interviews with 5 different healthcare facilities in Mumbai**. These facilities were selected through the **purposive sampling** method to ensure a sample that encompassed the various kinds of healthcare setups and their BMW management practices. The interviews were conducted using a **structured interview** schedule that was designed to include **close-ended** (yes/no) questions as well as a series of **open-ended questions**. All these questions were aimed at understanding current BMWM practices, segregation and storage methods, level of awareness regarding regulations and hazards associated with improper disposal and availability of infrastructure and resources for waste management. Secondary data, in the form of **reviewing existing literature**, was also used to gain insight into the background of BMWM practices in India.

Certain **limitations** that need to be considered with respect to this research are the small sample size which could lead to **limited generalizability** of the data collected, and the self-reporting nature of the data which could cause **bias on the part of the respondents** and produce less accurate results. Yet overall, the methodology adopted aims to offer a nuanced and holistic look at the status and challenges of BMW management in Mumbai.

Analysis –

The analysis aims to effectively grapple with the BMWM practices in depth along with their shortcomings, the awareness of medical practitioners and the extent to which the guidelines given under the BMWM Rules, 2016 are followed. Owing to the substantial nature of the data collected, each question has been analysed separately. This is to ensure that the presentation and interpretation of the data are presented in a comprehensive manner.

1. What kind of medical practice do you work in?

The research sample consisted of 5 healthcare facilities (HCFs) which included **2 hospitals, 1 dental clinic, 1 dermatology clinic and 1 pathology laboratory**. Their names have been omitted from the report in the interest of confidentiality of the participants. This sample ensures a well-rounded approach that takes into account the BMWM practices of a diverse set of healthcare facilities. All these practices are **private** and are all located in **Suburban Mumbai**.

2. What kind of waste does your practice produce?

Based on the 8 categories of biomedical waste given by WHO, the researcher found the types of waste produced by each practice. **General waste**, which was **found in all** the healthcare facilities, refers to solid waste from hospitals such as paper, cardboard, food waste and so on. **Pathological** waste includes human tissues, organs, biopsy samples, human placenta removed during childbirth, etc. and this type was found only in the **2 hospitals**. Found in **only 1 hospital** **radioactive waste** includes things like contaminated clothing or protective gear used during radiation therapy or discarded radioactive sources used in diagnostic imaging. **Chemical** waste such as mercury-containing devices like thermometers, laboratory solvents and agents was reportedly found in only the **2 hospitals**. All **5 HCFs produced infectious, pharmaceutical and sharps waste**. Infectious waste involves blood-soaked bandages or dressings, used needles or syringes, etc. while pharmaceutical waste is any vaccine vials or syringes, expired or unused medications and so on. Sharps waste refers to needles, syringes, broken glassware, scalpels, etc. Finally, **pressurised containers of waste** like inhalers, aerosol cans containing disinfectants or medication, and medical devices containing compressed gases or liquids were found in **3 HCFs – 2 hospitals and 1 dermatology clinic**.

It is important to note that all of this waste needs to be disposed of and treated in different ways owing to the distinct nature of each of the types.

3. Does your waste include hazardous waste in solid and liquid form?

Hazardous waste in solid form was produced by all the HCFs in the sample. However, this question was to gauge the nature and management practice of liquid hazardous waste. Apart from the dental clinic, **liquid hazardous waste** was found in all the practices. In the pathology laboratory, **bodily fluids** such as blood and urine testing samples were a major form of liquid hazardous waste along with **liquid chemicals and reagents** used in laboratory tests which include acids, bases, solvents, and dyes. These are **toxic and flammable** in nature and thus, must be dealt with extreme caution. In hospitals too, liquid hazardous waste in the form of the blood, urine and other bodily fluids of patients is present. Moreover, **IV solutions, cooling fluids, expired or unused liquid drugs**, hazardous chemicals such as **bleach, and phenols** used to prevent spreading or contamination are also present. In the dermatology clinic, while the volume is much less compared to hospitals and pathology labs, liquid hazardous waste in certain forms is found. This includes solutions used in chemical peels such as **glycolic acid, salicylic acid, trichloroacetic acid, liquid nitrogen** that is often used to treat warts and moles as well as solvents such as **acetone and ethyl acetate**. All of these are hazardous as either they are **corrosive** (the solutions in chemical peels) or they are **flammable and toxic** (the solvents) or due to its extremely cold temperature, the liquid nitrogen could cause potential **skin and tissue damage if not treated properly**. This further underlines the need for effective BMWM practices.

4. Is the liquid waste directly discharged into the sewer system?

All the respondents in the sample reported that their liquid waste was not directly discharged into the sewer system. However, it is important to consider that in situations like when **blood is spit in the sink** in the dental clinic, or **blood is washed off in sinks** in the hospitals it is possibly entering the sewer system directly.

5. Do you have your own treatment or disposal mechanisms?

None of the 5 HCFs have any provisions of their own for the treatment or disposal of the waste they produce. When asked if they were aware of methods such as **autoclaving or microwaving** that could aid in the on-site treatment of waste, the respondents reported having **autoclave machines for disinfecting the equipment that is reused** but not for disinfecting any of the waste materials. The general response was that the **job of treatment and disposal** of medical waste was of **those who collected the waste** from these facilities. None of them were aware of the microwaving and plasma pyrolysis methods.

6. Who comes to collect waste in your area?

SMS Envoclean Private Limited is the company that collects the waste from all 5 facilities and from a total of **11,037 clients**. Their plant is located in **Deonar** which has an **incinerator, autoclave, chemical disinfection and shredding facilities**. They gained authorization from the **Maharashtra Pollution Control Board in 2007** and are working in accordance with the Biomedical Waste Management Rules, 2016.

Interestingly, the facility is located just **near the Deonar landfill**, granting easy access to dump the garbage there. The Indian Express reported in 2023 that in this facility “while **4,500 to 5,500 metric tonnes of waste is processed** daily through bio-reactor technology and windrow composting, the **remaining waste is sent to the Deonar landfill**” (Acharya, 2023).

7. How many coloured bags do you use to dispose the waste?

Segregation of waste is an extremely crucial step of the waste management process. It ensures the **safe handling** and disposal of waste by **reducing the risk of exposure** to hazardous pathogens and toxins present in medical waste. Moreover, proper segregation practices will also prevent soil, water and land pollution and **promote environmental sustainability**. The failure to correctly segregate waste can lead to **serious health risks** for waste handlers, healthcare workers and the general public. Thus, for safeguarding public health and the environment along with the integrity of the waste management process, segregation is key.

To understand the segregation practices of the HCFs in question, they were asked how many coloured bags they used and how they segregated their waste. Since all the facilities are using the same waste collection service (i.e. SMS Envoclean), they follow the same segregation practices too. All HCFs segregate their waste in **2 coloured bags and one box**. The **yellow bag** is used for **soiled waste** like blood-soaked cotton or bandages, **chemical or clinical waste**, etc. while the **red bag** is used for used **gloves, masks, catheters, medicine vials, plastic bags or bottles**, etc. The used **syringes, needles, scalpels and sharp metals** are put in a **separate box**.

In accordance with the BMW Rules, 2016, the **yellow and red bags are being used by these HCFs effectively**. The **white bag** that is supposed to contain the needles, syringes and other sharp metals has been **replaced by a box**. The **blue bag** is to be used for glassware such as medicine vials and ampoules along with metallic body implants. However, the glassware is not being separately put in a different bag, it is reportedly **added to the red bag itself**.

8. How often is waste collected from your practice?

The **hospitals** in the sample reported that their biomedical **waste was collected every day**. The **dental clinic and pathology lab** reported that due to the **lesser volume** of their waste, it was only collected **once every week**. For the **dermatology clinic**, it was collected **once every 2 weeks**.

According to the **BMWM Rules, 2016**, biomedical waste is **not supposed to be stored for more than 48 hours**. This is to **minimise the risk of accumulating** potentially hazardous waste on-site that could lead to **cross-contamination, pest infections and bad odour**. Timely disposal is important to maintain **hygienic conditions** and also prevent the risks previously mentioned. In addition, strict adherence to storage time limits is **mandated by the guidelines** provided by the State and thus, ensures compliance with regulatory requirements.

9. Are you aware of the government's biomedical waste management rules and regulations?

None of the HCFs from the sample **were aware** of the BMWWM guidelines provided by the government. A common response was that they were only **doing what their waste collection company had mandated**. Thus, it can be assumed that awareness in general in most HCFs in Mumbai is lacking significantly. As a result, the efficiency and viability of segregation, storage, disposal and handling of BMW is largely under question.

Increased awareness is required not only to ensure proper disposal and management practices but also to instil **accountability and responsibility** in the HCFs. This would promote the implementation of **sustainable and safe management practices** as well as empower all HCFs to **contribute positively to public health outcomes** and become more **environmentally conscious**.

10. What are the annual cost considerations associated with the collection of your waste?

Both the hospitals pay around **Rs. 10,000 annually** to SMS Envoclean, while the **other HCFs** i.e. the pathology lab, the dermatology clinic and the dental clinic pay around **Rs. 5000 – 6000**.

11. Would you be willing to pay more for better BMW management?

All except for one of the HCFs said that they were unwilling to pay more for better BMW. They were of the opinion that the **current practices were acceptable** and that they were **already paying enough**. This shows a **prioritisation of cost-saving measures** rather than environmental and public health concerns which could have **long-term effects** on sustainability and safety.

12. Do you have trained personnel handling your waste?

None of the HCFs had trained personnel handling their waste segregation or disposal. All of them reported that either the **nurses, the clinic's assistants or other clerical staff** would generally handle it.

13. Do you provide safety equipment like gloves, masks, aprons, etc. to those who handle the waste in your practice?

All the HCFs reported to providing safety and protective equipment such as gloves, masks and aprons to their workers that handle waste. This is an extremely crucial practice as it ensures **no cross contamination** which could lead to skin damage, infections, certain diseases, etc. and **reduces the risk of any type of exposure.**

14. Are you aware of any training programs/ courses for BMW disposal?

Not a single one of the HCFs are aware of any training programs for BMW. However, many such programs are offered all over the country. The **Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB)** and many **State Pollution Control Boards (SPCBs)** in India provide training programs and workshops for healthcare professionals, waste handlers, and regulatory authorities. The **National Accreditation Board for Hospitals & Healthcare Providers (NABH)** is a constituent board of the Quality Council of India (QCI) and this offers accreditation standards for healthcare facilities which includes requirements related to biomedical waste management. Along with this, they also have several training and awareness programs to ensure compliance with the standards they expect. **NGOs** such as Toxics Link, Centre for Occupational and Environmental Health, Society for Environment and Development and Centre for Environment Education all provide awareness workshops, training sessions and programs regarding waste management which includes BMW which is relevant for all stakeholders including HCFs and waste handlers. Certain **private companies** that are in the BMW field also have their own training and awareness programs, SMS Envoclean does too according to its website.

15. Are there any measures made to reduce the volume of waste produced?

None of the HCFs are making any efforts to reduce the volume of waste they generate. As the dental clinic, pathology lab and dermatology clinic see it, they are **not generating that great a volume of waste** in the first place. The hospitals and the other HCFs too report that all the waste generated is **unavoidable or impossible to reduce**.

However, methods such as **promoting reusable appliances** that reduce the need for single-use medical equipment, devices and textiles or **creating effective disinfection, shredding and other on-site treatment facilities** could be seen as solutions to reducing the volume of waste at the source itself.

16. Are there any mechanisms you use to reduce the toxicity of waste before disposing it?

Just like in the case of reducing the volume of waste, **none of the HCFs** are making efforts to reduce its toxicity either. One common response was that it was **not their job** to disinfect anything or reduce the toxicity. They were **merely following the instructions** provided by the waste collecting company which did the job of disinfection and reducing or disposing toxic waste.

The strategies of **on-site treatment options like autoclaving or microwaving** could help treat toxic waste within the HCFs themselves. This would bring down any chances of the **spreading of infections and diseases and limit any exposure** to waste handlers, healthcare workers and the general public while also leading to increased environmental sustainability.

17. Are you aware of the hazards that can arise from improper BMWM?

4 out of 5 HCFs were reported that they were aware of the hazards that could arise from improper BMWM. When asked to elaborate on these hazards, the most commonly mentioned response was that exposure to **syringes or needles could lead to infections** if not handled with caution. Some of them specified that diseases like **AIDS or HIV** were possible from contact with these used syringes. A less common but mentioned response was that not disposing of waste correctly could lead to the **BMW ending up with solid waste** and since there is no disinfection mechanism here, it would lead to the spread of diseases and infections here too.

None of the HCFs mentioned any of the environmental costs or hazards that are associated with improper BMWM.

18. Do you think any challenges exist with BMWM currently? If yes, what are they?

While one of the HCFs was not sure of any challenges, the other 4 were clear in their view. **2 were of the opinion that challenges did indeed exist** while the other **2 seemed completely content and saw no issues** with current BMWM practices.

One of the challenges mentioned by a HCF was that there was **little to no awareness regarding government regulations**, and while they recognised it was their duty to know of them, they stated that they were never made to comply or urged to learn more about BMWM systems prescribed by the State. The other HCF mentioned that one major challenge was the **growing volume of BMW in recent years**.

19. On a scale of 1-5 how satisfied are you with BMW currently?

Despite the response to the previous question that varied a little, the response here was generally positive. Of the 5 HCFs, **2 said they were very satisfied** with the BMW practices, while **2 others put themselves on 4** on the scale suggesting they were quite satisfied as well. Only one HCF gave a **rating of 3 and this was due to the high cost** they believed was associated with BMW. The general response was that the management is **smoothly practised** with little to no complaints regarding the services provided by SMS Envoclean. Until now, **none of them have ever encountered any issues** or felt any hazards that are associated with improper management of their waste.

Conclusion –

In recent years, the volume of biomedical waste has grown exponentially. Factors such as advancements in medical knowledge and technology leading to increased healthcare services, a stark rise in population and thus, a rise in the number of patients, the changing lifestyles fuelling sedentary and overall unhealthy ways of living along with greater mental health issues due to the current fast-paced socio-economic and political climate have all contributed to the increase in BMW. Thus, there is an urgent need for proactive measures that address and successfully manage the rising rate of BMW being produced.

It is evident from the findings of this study that there have been some commendable efforts made towards BMWM in the form of waste segregation and provision of safety equipment to waste handlers since these are some of the most integral things to consider in order to avoid health risks. Yet, in many areas, the current systems are lacking. Most notably the awareness regarding government guidelines and regulations is severely low with most HCFs relying solely on the directives provided by their waste collection company. Additionally, it is evident that environmental costs are rarely even considered in conversations circling BMWM. Thus, these are some recommendations to ensure better BMWM practices:

- Education and awareness training programs need to be prioritised among all stakeholders i.e. the waste handlers, the healthcare professionals and the general public too. This could be in the form of regular workshops, seminars, certification courses and public awareness campaigns which would encourage individuals on all levels to adopt safe and sustainable BMWM practices.
- This research has underscored the need for and importance of on-site treatment methods and facilities within medical practices. Autoclaving and microwaving are the most significant methods that can be considered and those HCFs that have the resources can also consider plasma pyrolysis. This would reduce the toxicity of waste and mitigate those health and environmental hazards that are associated with transport and delayed treatment.
- HCFs need to actively pursue waste reduction strategies by integrating effective disinfection mechanisms, promoting reusable medical devices and equipment as well as adopting any new and innovative technologies that would aid in reducing the volume of waste at the source.

- Regulatory authorities must ensure better compliance by introducing more stringent and regular audits that force HCFs to adhere to the protocols provided by them. Private companies handling waste also need to be regulated and audited more strictly to make certain they follow the code and conduct provided by the State. Rigorous consequences in the form of fines or penalties need to be felt by those that are not in accordance with the guidelines provided to guarantee compliance.
- In all the processes involved, from the disposing of waste as currently being practised, to the installation of new technology for better treatment of waste, to the formation of legislation regarding more suitable waste management techniques, at each level, the environmental costs must not be ignored under any circumstances. In fact, actively creating and using environmentally sound mechanisms to manage waste should be a priority in itself.

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Annexure –

Questionnaire used for this study:

1. What part of Mumbai is your practice located in?
2. What kind of medical practice do you work in?
3. What kind of waste does your practice produce?
4. Does the waste produced in your practice include hazardous waste in solid and liquid form?
5. Is the liquid hazardous waste directly discharged into the sewer system?
6. Do you have your own treatment and disposal mechanisms for management of waste?
7. Who comes to collect the waste from your practice?
8. How many coloured bags do you use to dispose the waste your practice produces?
9. How often is waste collected from your practice?
10. Are you aware of the government's rules and regulations regarding BMWM?
11. What are the annual cost considerations of BMWM?
12. Would you be willing to pay more for better BMWM?
13. Do you have trained personnel handling your waste?
14. Do you provide safety equipment like gloves, masks, aprons, etc. to those who handle the waste in your practice?
15. Are you aware of any training programs/ courses for BMW disposal?
16. Are there any measures made to reduce the volume of waste produced?
17. Are there any mechanisms you use to reduce the toxicity of waste before disposing it?
18. Are you aware of the hazards that can arise from improper BMWM?
19. Do you think any challenges exist with BMWM currently? If yes, what are they?
20. On a scale of 1-5 how satisfied are you with BMWM currently?